

1 **Utilization of alternative energy sources during metastasis in humans.**

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7 Metastasis is the primary and proximal cause of death in humans with cancer. Cancer is defined by
8 unrestricted proliferation or unscheduled cell cycle progression. Metastasis at a foreign site is established
9 at some point later than when the primary tumor is established, early or late in the course of disease. We
10 describe here mobilization of alternative energy sources during metastasis to distant organ sites in
11 humans with cancer. A primary cellular system affected in metastasis that evolved despite apparent
12 restriction of proliferative capacity was the ribosome. Cellular evolution which proceeds concurrent with
13 adaptive energy utilization changes in cancer occurs not only through energy sensing hubs that function in
14 homeostasis like mTOR but through the repurposing of systems that function in translational capacity like
15 the ribosome. Metastasis at a foreign site does not require dissemination of a progenitor with proliferative
16 potential and can proceed through alternative energy utilization modes.
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